

Development And Evaluation Of An Egcg Cross-Linked Glycol Chitosan–Pectin Nanogel For Controlled Delivery Of Apigenin In Chronic Wound Healing

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ABSTRACT

Chronic wounds, especially diabetic wounds, are difficult to manage due to inflammation and oxidative stress. This study aimed to develop and evaluate an Apigenin-loaded glycol chitosan–pectin nanogel cross-linked with epigallocatechin gallate (EGCG) for improved wound healing. Nanogels were prepared via polyelectrolyte complexation and characterized for physicochemical properties, encapsulation efficiency, rheology, swelling behavior, particle size, zeta potential, in vitro drug release, and stability. The optimized formulation (F5) exhibited suitable pH (7.2), high encapsulation efficiency (93.40±2.92%), desirable viscosity (382±8.55 cP), and good spreadability. Particle size analysis confirmed nanoscale distribution (90 nm, PDI 0.212) with adequate colloidal stability (−24.26±0.86 mV). The formulation demonstrated high swelling capacity and sustained drug release up to 12 h following Higuchi diffusion kinetics with non-Fickian transport behavior. Stability studies showed no significant changes under accelerated conditions for three months. The developed nanogel system demonstrates promising potential as a stable, controlled-release, and multifunctional wound healing formulation.

Keywords: Apigenin, Nanogel, Glycol chitosan, Pectin, EGCG, Wound healing, Controlled release, Polyelectrolyte complex

INTRODUCTION

Treatment of chronic wound is always challenging and it becomes more difficult especially in case of diabetic wounds. Inflammation, oxidative stress such factors makes it difficult to treat the chronic wounds. Therefore ideal wound dressing material should be developed in such way that it will counteract all these issue. It should be able to minimize the infection, able to control the oxidative stress and should be effectively involved in management of haemostasis, inflammation, proliferation, and remodelling.^[1,2]

Therefore use of natural flavonoids is much needed approach for treatment for wound healing. As flavonoids are phenolic compounds which are present in large amount in fruits, vegetables, herbs, cocoa, chocolate, tea, soy, red wine, and other plant food and beverage products.^[3-6]^[26]

Flavonoids are used in wound-healing properties due to their anti-inflammatory, angiogenesis, re-epithelialization, and antioxidant effects. Some flavonoids are also known to control blood sugar level. Therefore when flavonoids are used to treat the wound it will show synergistic effect and wound healing process will be accelerated.^[3-6]

Apigenin—a naturally occurring flavone—has demonstrated potent anti-inflammatory effects in various models by modulating NF-κB, MAPK, and JAK/STAT signalling. Notably, the JAK1/STAT3 pathway is a key regulator of cytokine production in macrophages and has been implicated in chronic inflammatory skin conditions. This pathway is particularly relevant in perianal abscess and postoperative wounds, as it mediates inflammation amplification and tissue repair imbalance in chronic inflammatory skin injuries.^[7-9]

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Nanogel a three-dimensional nanoscale networks of cross-linked hydrophilic polymers, offer a superior option for wound healing applications. [10-13]

Their special design provides great biocompatibility, adjustable porosity for gas exchange, and high water absorption to provide a moist wound environment this fascinates the wound healing process. It possesses unique advantages such as biocompatibility and versatile drug delivery capabilities, which makes this formulation unique as compared to others. [26]It holds high water-absorption capacity which maintains a moist wound environment, which accelerates the wound healing and also provides a protective barrier. Due to smaller in size it can deeply penetrate the tissue which helps for localized treatment. [26]

Nanogels have the ability to promote keratinocyte and fibroblast activity, which is essential for re-epithelialization. They are also known to promote angiogenesis, or the formation of new blood vessels. [26]Crucially, their mucoadhesive qualities and nanoscale size improve proximity and contact time with the wound bed, allowing the therapeutic drug to be released locally and sustainably to the target site. It also offers better stability, greater drug loading capacity, and the capacity to react to particular wound microenvironment stimuli (such as pH and enzymes) in comparison to other nanocarriers (such as liposomes and polymeric nanoparticles), resulting in a "smart" release profile that corresponds with healing dynamics.

Glycol chitosan a cationic polysaccharide derived from chitin is the best biopolymer for wound healing formulations. Its natural hemostatic qualities support the first stage of clotting. [14-17]Antibacterial property of chitosan aids in the prevention of infection which is significant wound care benefit. Its positive charge extends residence time by encouraging mucoadhesion to the negatively charged wound surface. [14-17] [26]It is also found to involve in increasing fibroblast proliferation, stimulation of macrophage activation for efficient debridement, and encourages the deposition of organized collagen, all of which directly leads to increased the therapeutic action of the loaded medication in developed formulation. [26]

Chitosan is frequently used with anionic polymers, such as pectin, to create a polyelectrolyte complex

that modifies the release profile and improves stability. The benefits of both chitosan's bioactivity and pectin's biocompatibility and gel forming capacity are combined in this way. [14-17] [18,19]

This study suggests using green tea extract (GTE) as a natural, multifunctional cross-linker in accordance with green chemistry principles. GTE, which is rich in polyphenols like epigallocatechin gallate (EGCG), can cross-link chitosan chains via hydrogen bonding and Michael addition reactions. If conventional cross-linkers used to stabilize such networks (e.g., glutaraldehyde) raise toxicity concerns. [14-17] [20-22] [26]This creates a tri-therapeutic system that combines nanogel, chitosan, and green tea polyphenols while also strengthening the gel network and adding its own antioxidant and anti-inflammatory qualities. [14-17] [20-22]. Thus, the goal of this research is to create, describe, and assess a new, simplified Apigenin loaded chitosan pectin cross-linked nanogel that is based on a chitosan-pectin polyelectrolyte complex and cross-linked with green tea extract. [7-9] [14-17] [18,19] [20-22]

This design combines the multi-target therapeutic activity of nanogel with the wound-healing synergy of chitosan, all given via an innovative nanogel substrate supported by a bioactive cross-linker. [14-17]It is expected that the formulation will improve nanogel's solubility, stability, and targeted distribution to the wound site, providing a thorough, efficient, and environmentally safe approach to advanced wound care.

MATERIALS

Glycol Chitosan (CAS No. 9012-76-4) was procured from HiMedia Laboratories Pvt. Ltd. (Mumbai, India). Pectin powder (CAS No. 71010-52- 1) was obtained from the MP Biomedicals. Apigenin was obtained from Yucca laboratories Mumbai. All other materials used were of analytical grade. [7-9] [14-17] [18,19]

Epigallocatechin gallate (EGCG) was purchased from Yucca laboratories. Aloe vera juice was freshly prepared in the laboratory. Acetic acid, glycerine, sodium hydroxide, and other analytical grade reagents were supplied by [company]. Double-distilled water was used throughout the study. [20-22]

FORMULATION OF NANO GEL

A. Preparation of Nanogel-Chitosan Nanoparticles (Using EGCG Cross-linker) ^{[14-17] [20-22]}

Dissolve accurately weighed chitosan in varying concentration ranging from 0.2% to 0.6% in 100 ml of 1 % acetic acid solution. Accurately weighed 0.05 g of nanogel powder is added to chitosan solution. Sonicate the above solution for 10 minutes. Dissolve the 0.02 g of pure EGCG in 50 ml of distilled water, solution is filtered through Whatman filter paper. Chitosan nanogel solution is placed on magnetic stirrer and stirrer is rotated at 500 rpm, add EGCG crosslinker solution to chitosan nanogel solution in dropwise manner slowly (1ml/min.) using syringe. The solution was stirred continuously 2 hours at room temperature. Nanogel-loaded chitosan nanoparticles cross-linked with EGCG is produced. ^{[14-17] [20-22]}

B. Preparation of Pectin Gel Base ^[18,19]

50 ml of aloe vera is taken in beaker and pectin powder of varying concentration ranging from 0.25 to 0.75.00 % was added. Pectin powder was slowly sprinkled with continuous stirring. It is stirred at temperature of 40 °C) to get clear gel. Finally 5 ml of glycerine is added to above gel base. ^[18,19]

C. Formulation of Nanogel

Nanoparticle suspension is slowly added to pectin gel base and thoroughly stirred using homogenizer 5000 rpm for five minutes. If needed final volume is adjusted using distilled water and pH is maintained using NaOH solution. Finally Nanogel nanogel is developed. ^[18,19]

Table No. 1: Different Formulation of Nanogels

Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
Nanogel (g)	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05
Chitosan (g)	0.20	0.40	0.60	0.60	0.20
1% Acetic acid (ml)	100	100	100	100	100
EGCG (g)	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02
Aloe vera juice (ml)	50	50	50	50	50
Pectin (g)	0.125	0.250	0.375	0.00	0.250
Glycerine (ml)	5	5	5	5	5
Distilled water (for EGCG) (ml)	50	50	50	50	50

CHARACTERIZATION OF NANO GEL:

1 Physical characteristic

The prepared nanogel formulations were inspected visually for their homogeneity, consistency and phase separation.

2 Determination of pH

The pH was determined by digital pH meter. One gram of gel was dissolved in 25 ml of distilled water and the pH electrode was then dipped in to gel formulation for 30 min until constant reading obtained. Then constant reading was noted. The measurement of pH of each formulation was done in triplicate and average values were calculated.

3. Rheological study

Rheological study was performed using Brookfield digital viscometer with spindle No. 6 to measure viscosity at different shear rates. The appropriate wide mouth container was filled with the required quantity of nanogel in such a way that it should be able to adequately allow the spindle of the viscometer to be dipped. Viscosity (centipoises) of prepared nanogel was measured at 10-100 rpm at 25 ±1°C.

4. Spreadability

Two standard-sized (6x2) glass slides were used. One of the slides was covered with the formulation whose spreadability was to be determined.

Determination of spreadability helps us to ensure that the medication can be easily applied and uniformly distributed over the skin.

$$\text{Spreadability} = m \times l / t$$

Where, S = Spreadability (g cm/sec), m = weight tied to the upper slide (20 grams),

l = length of glass slide (6cms), t = time taken in seconds

5. Drug encapsulation efficiency

In order to extract the drug from the prepared formulation, it was placed in 50 mL of buffer solution (pH 7.4) and vigorously agitated for 24 hours. After filtering the sample in buffer solution, it was measured at 338 nm using a UV spectrophotometer.

The encapsulation efficiency was calculated using the following equations:

$$\% \text{ Entrapment efficiency (\%)} = \text{Actual drug content / theoretical drug content} \times 100$$

6. Swelling behaviour

An essential characteristic of nanogel, particularly when applied to exuding wounds, is its tendency to swell. Swelling ratio of prepared formulation was evaluated in water and buffer solutions of pH 7.4. Accurately weighted amount of dried gels was kept in water and buffer solutions separately. The nanogel was removed after specific time intervals and the surface is wiped off. The weight was measured and again kept into the same medium. This process was repeated with time interval of 30 min until a constant weight was obtained. Swelling ratio was calculated by the following equation:

$$SR = (W_t - W_0) / W_0$$

Where, W_0 is the initial weight of dry nanogel and W_t is the weight of the swollen nanogel at time 't' at temperature 37°C. This study was repeated thrice, and average values were observed

7. Determination Zeta potential

The zeta potential was characterized by using a Malvern Zetasizer (Nano ZS 90, Malvern Ltd., UK). Prior to the measurements, 1 mg of prepared

formulation was diluted with 10 ml of double-distilled water in a volumetric flask, mixed with vigorous shaking to produce appropriate scattering intensity. The measurements were made at an angle of 90° at 25°C.

8. Surface Morphological study

Scanning Electron Microscopy was used to perform morphological study. The prepared nanogel was dried for 24 hours using freeze dryer (-60°C). The accelerating voltage of 20kV was applied and dried nanogel deposited on platinum to define network structure.

9. In-vitro drug release study

In vitro diffusion study of was carried using Franz diffusion cell equipped with semipermeable (MWCO 12–14 kDa) cellophane membrane. Semipermeable cellophane was soaked 24 hours in phosphate buffer pH 7.4 then mounted between donor and receiver compartments of the Franz diffusion cell. The receptor cell (15 ml capacity) was filled with phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) and continuously rotated with magnetic stirrer at a speed of 100 rpm. Formulation applied through donor compartment on the dialysis membrane. The system was adjusted at 37±0.5 °C throughout study. [23]. An accurately weighed quantity (1 g) of apigenin-loaded nanogel was placed in the donor compartment. Aliquots 0.5 ml were taken out at specific time intervals after every hour (1, 2, 4, 6, 8, 12 h) and replaced with same volume of fresh buffer solution of pH 7.4 to maintain sink condition. The samples were analysed spectrophotometrically at 338 nm against phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) as a blank. Drug concentration was determined using a previously established calibration curve of apigenin in phosphate buffer (pH 7.4). The cumulative amount of drug release was calculated. [7–9]. All experiments were performed in triplicate, and results were expressed as mean ± SD. Release kinetics were evaluated by fitting the data to zero-order, first-order, Higuchi, and Korsmeyer–Peppas models. [24,25]

10. Particle Size Analysis and Polydispersity Index (PDI)

The particle size and polydispersity index (PDI) of the optimized Apigenin-loaded nanogel (F5) were determined using dynamic light scattering (Malvern

Zetasizer Nano ZS) at 25 °C after appropriate dilution with double-distilled water. [7-9]

11. Stability Studies

To investigate the quality of the prepared formulation under the effects of external factors such temperature, humidity, and light, stability testing was carried out. It is necessary to determine the recommended shelf life, retest duration, and storage conditions. The stability test required for drug registration applications in the United States, Japan, and the European Union is outlined in the International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) Guidelines titled "Stability testing of New Drug substance and product" (QIA). [26]

Nanogel was stored in glass vials at temperature $25\pm 0.2^\circ\text{C}$ and $60\pm 5\%$ relative humidity in a stability chamber. Accelerated stability testing was performed at a temperature ($40\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$) and relative humidity $75\pm 5\%$ and at $30\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, $65\pm 5\%$ for 3 months. Samples were taken at regular time intervals of 1 month for over a period of 3 months and take observation for any change.

RESULT & DISCUSSION

1. Physical characteristics

All formulations were evaluated for homogeneity, consistency and phase separation. It was found that all formulations were found to be of excellent homogeneous, good consistency and no phase separation was noticed in any formulation.

2. pH determination

The pH of Apigenin loaded nanogel was found to be between the ranges of 6.7 to 7.1. [7-9]

There was no too much difference between the pH of all types of Apigenin loaded nanogel. [7-9]

The pH was 6.7, 7.1, 7.1, 6.8 and 7.2 for Formulation F1, F2, F3 and F4 and F5 respectively.

3. Rheological studies

Inverse relationship between shear rate and viscosity of nanogel was noticed. It was clear that as the shear rate increased the viscosity of nanogel decreased and vice versa. The viscosity of nanogel is modified due to interaction between two matrixes. Decrease in viscosity of nanogel with respect to increase in shear rate, indicates that the nanogel belonged to a non-newtonian pseudo-plastic fluid due to the typical shear thinning behavior. Increase in viscosity with increasing concentration of Glycol chitosan and pectin was found from F1 to F3 and F5. [14-17] [18,19]

It was earlier discussed that increased concentration of polymer may result in higher degree of crosslinking. In case of the F4 formulation lowest viscosity was observed as single polymer is present.

In case of Apigenin loaded nanogel the value of viscosity was found to be 94 ± 3.90 , 279 ± 6.27 , 308 ± 8.07 , 88 ± 9.77 , and 382 ± 8.55 centipoise for F1, F2, F3, F4 and F5 formulation respectively. [7-9]

Table No. 2: Rheological observation of Apigenin Nanogel [7-9]

Shear rate (rpm)	Viscosity of different Apigenin nanogel formulations (centipoises)				
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
10	509 ± 11.65	741 ± 18.57	831 ± 19.27	501 ± 14.90	1011 ± 25.37
20	458 ± 9.86	614 ± 13.66	744 ± 18.89	452 ± 6.31	869 ± 19.58
30	397 ± 8.35	554 ± 12.12	670 ± 17.45	376 ± 7.46	759 ± 17.79
40	272 ± 6.87	508 ± 11.07	603 ± 15.75	249 ± 9.50	677 ± 15.45

50	232±5.74	440±10.88	525±12.24	219±2.19	555±13.27
60	194±4.25	406±9.67	469±10.61	187±4.18	487±11.66
70	176±4.20	361±8.34	386±9.85	161±7.27	461±10.86
80	142±4.07	320±8.04	353±9.67	123±1.09	426±9.81
90	112±4.09	285±7.65	319±8.18	103±6.21	409±9.57
100	94±3.90	279±6.27	308±8.07	88±9.77	382±8.55

4. Spreadability Study

The Spreadability of all Apigenin loaded nanogel was between the ranges of 13.40^[7-9]

g.cm/sec to 11.21 g.cm/sec.

Lower the value of Spreadability the better the ability of gel to spread easily on surface. Easily spreadable formulation covers the affected surface and therefore improves the diffusion of drug from dosage forms to site of application.

5. Drug encapsulation efficiency

Table No. 3: Spreadability and drug encapsulation efficiency of different Apigenin nanogel^[7-9]

Formulation	Spreadability (g.cm/sec)	Drug encapsulation efficiency (%)
F1	13.40	72.12±1.02
F2	12.62	81.34±4.17
F3	12.42	87.74±2.07
F4	11.21	69.51±5.02
F5	9.21	93.40±2.92

6. Swelling behavior

The swelling ratio of prepared nanogel was compared and highest swelling ratio of Apigenin loaded Glycol chitosan pectin cross-linked nanogel with optimized formulation F5 was observed.^{[7-9][14-17][18,19]}

Higher swelling ratio of Apigenin loaded Glycol chitosan pectin cross-linked nanogel at 240 minutes was indicating the higher water absorption capacity of nanogel. The study of swelling rate is a determinant of drug uptake. The gradual rise in swelling ratio with time was observed may be due to presence of Glycol chitosan. The hydrophilicity of Glycol group in the Glycol chitosan increases with time reported already.

The drug entrapment efficiency of optimized prepared Apigenin nanogel was found to be 93.40±2.92%.^[7-9]

It was noted that drug entrapment increased with increasing the concentration up to certain limit. The enhancement of drug entrapment efficiency could be the formation of higher cross-linking density. Increase in drug entrapment efficiency with increasing amount of polymer may be due to greater hydrogen bonding interaction between drug and polymer.

Swelling capacity plays an important role in wound healing, specifically in exudating wounds. Nanogel with high swelling ratio can absorb moderate amount of the wound exudates by swelling which leads to formation of a dry bed of wound that further accelerates the healing process. Apigenin loaded Glycol chitosan pectin cross-linked nanogel i.e. F5 formulation exhibited higher swelling ratio in phosphate buffer pH 7.4, it could be beneficial for wound healing process.^{[7-9][14-17][18,19][26]}

The higher swelling ratio also confirms about good porous nature of nanogel having larger surface area.

Table No. 4: Swelling ration of different Apigenin nanogel^[7-9]

Time (minutes)	Swelling ratio of Apigenin nanogel (%)				
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
30	51.60±1.62	54.61±1.62	55.31±1.84	29.07±0.84	67.10±1.84
60	87.71±2.16	86.76±2.16	90.43±2.51	62.52±1.26	101.62±2.85
90	109.22±2.88	112.23±2.88	106.64±3.20	71.62±1.91	125.04±3.27
120	134.14±3.61	137.14±3.61	137.24±2.86	75.44±1.84	139.52±3.10
150	141.61±3.88	145.60±3.88	149.12±4.07	75.89±1.67	149.65±3.75
180	144.39±3.02	146.40±3.02	150.20±4.02	76.69±1.28	154.82±3.95
210	145.02±3.98	147.04±3.98	152.21±3.98	77.43±1.70	156.46±3.89
240	146.37±4.13	147.36±4.13	153.34±4.13	78.45±1.84	157.28±4.20

7. Zeta Potential

The importance of the zeta potential evaluation is due to its relation to the stability of colloidal dispersions. If zeta potential value in modulus is small, the attraction between the droplets is greater than the

repulsion, which can lead to the flocculation and breakage of the dispersion. The zeta potential of optimized formulation was found to be -24.26 ± 0.86 mV which indicates a good physical stability.^[26]

8. Surface Morphological Study

The surface morphology of the apigenin-loaded glycol chitosan-pectin cross-linked nanogel was examined using scanning electron microscopy

(SEM).^{[7-9] [14-17] [18,19]} Photomicrograph of different nanogel confirms that Apigenin loaded Glycol chitosan pectin cross-linked nanogel holds the continuous and porous structure. All observed pores

were found to be uniform with smooth walls. [7-9] [14-17] [18,19]

The SEM micrographs revealed a continuous, highly porous three-dimensional network with uniformly distributed pores and smooth pore walls. A higher degree of polymeric interaction is suggested by the smaller pore diameters, which enhances the produced nanogel's structural stability [10-13] [26]

The smaller pore size confirms about greater degree of crosslinking between polymers in developed formulation. The porous structures make it more capable to provide oxygen and nutrients to cells during wound healing reported that the high permeability for nutrients support to cellular growth by the nanogel due to the interconnected and mutually penetrating pores

Fig No. 1: Morphological observation of Optimized nanogel formulation

9. In vitro drug release study:

Table No. 5: Cumulative percent drug release study of Apigenin nanogel [7-9]

Time (hours)	Cumulative percent release of Apigenin Nanogel				
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
1	11.94±0.07	9.21±0.07	8.19±0.07	17.27±0.41	11.11±0.24
2	28.55±0.10	11.20±0.13	10.24±0.13	26.48±0.61	12.37±0.34
3	41.19±1.31	20.79±0.17	19.78±0.17	48.93±1.72	19.19±0.41
4	57.61±1.42	28.44±0.21	26.44±0.21	58.29±1.52	29.89±0.37
5	68.20±2.57	32.09±1.36	31.08±1.36	63.36±2.68	34.86±1.53
6	79.36±2.64	35.66±1.51	34.67±1.51	79.52±2.87	41.07±1.74

7	86.64±3.84	49.17±2.61	48.16±2.61	85.56±3.75	47.13±2.76
8	93.87±3.66	56.84±2.72	56.87±2.72	99.57±3.87	49.41±2.55
10	99.18±3.75	68.40±3.64	67.39±3.64	100	56.38±2.78
12	100	84.21±3.81	83.24±3.81	100	87.03±3.95

10. Particle Size Analysis and Polydispersity Index (PDI)

Table No. 6: Particle size analysis & polydispersity index of Apigenin nanogel [7-9]

Formulation Code	Mean hydrodynamic diameter (nm)	PDI
F1	85	0.191
F2	91	0.180
F3	110	0.201
F4	130	0.190
F5	90	0.212

The particle size and polydispersity index (PDI) of Apigenin-loaded nanogel formulations (F1–F5) was performed using dynamic light scattering. The mean value of hydrodynamic diameters was found to be between the range from 85 to 130 nm which confirms the formation of nanoscale systems. Among all formulations, F1, F2, and F5 exhibited comparatively smaller particle sizes of 85 nm, 91 nm, and 90 nm, respectively, whereas F3 and F4 showed slightly increased sizes, which may be due to higher polymer concentrations leads to enhanced cross-linking density. [7-9] [26]

The optimized formulation F5 demonstrated a mean particle size of 90 nm with a PDI value of 0.212, showing narrow size distribution and good colloidal homogeneity.

All PDI values for all formulations were found to be below 0.25, indicating uniform particle dispersion and minimal aggregation.

The nanoscale size of the prepared nanogels is advantageous for wound healing applications, as it increases surface contact with the wound bed and promotes localized drug delivery. Furthermore, the

low PDI values confirm formulation stability, which correlates well with the observed zeta potential of -24.26 ± 0.86 mV, indicating adequate electrostatic stabilization of the nanogel system. [26]

These results demonstrate that the chitosan–pectin polyelectrolyte complex cross-linked with EGCG successfully produced a stable nanosized formulation suitable for wound healing applications. [14-17] [18,19] [20-22]

11. Stability study

Data from stability studies shows no significant differences in physical appearance,

pH, viscosity, and drug content of Apigenin loaded nanogel. [7-9]

Apigenin loaded Nanogel found to be stable even after exposure to accelerated temperature and humidity conditions for a period of 3 months. [7-9]

Data obtained from stability studies of nanogel showed that loss of less than 1% of drug content in first month under room temperature and around 2 to 3% in 3 months.

Table No. 7: Stability study of Apigenin nanogel^[7-9]

Formulations	Temperature and humidity 25 ± 0.2 °C; 60% ± 5%			Temperature and humidity 40 ± 2 °C; 75 ± 5%		
	1 Month	2 Month	3 Month	1 Month	2 Month	3 Month
	F5	99.17 ± 2.21	98.42±2.21	97.78 ± 2.19	98.43 ± 2.16	97.69±3.19

12. Release Kinetics Study

On the basis of the cumulative drug release profiles, the Apigenin loaded nanogel formulations exhibited an initial sudden release followed by sustained drug release up to 12 h. The release pattern did not follow zero-order kinetics, as the drug release rate was not constant throughout the given time period. The formulations such as F1 and F2 showed partial first-order properties as having low polymer concentration; however, formulations F3, F4 and optimized formulation F5 does not follow first-order behavior.^[7-9]

CONCLUSION:

The release profiles of optimized formulations followed good compliance with the Higuchi model, indicating diffusion-controlled drug release from the chitosan–pectin polymeric matrix. Furthermore, considering the swelling behavior and rheological properties of nanogel, Korsmeyer–Peppas analysis suggests an anomalous (non-Fickian) transport mechanism, where drug release is followed by a combination of diffusion and polymer matrix relaxation. These results confirm that the developed Apigenin nanogel provides controlled and sustained drug delivery suitable for wound healing applications.^{[7-9] [14-17] [18,19] [24,25]}

The cumulative drug release of optimized formulation F5 was significantly higher compared to F3 and F4 ($p < 0.05$), confirming the influence of polymer concentration on release behavior. The best rheological properties of nanogel improve the retention time on skin surface which in turn results into increased bioavailability of nanogel.^[26]

Apigenin-loaded glycol chitosan–pectin nanogel cross-linked with EGCG showed good, high encapsulation efficiency, sustained drug release, and other desirable physicochemical properties. The formulation exhibits great promise as a multipurpose, environmentally friendly, and efficient wound healing solution that can be used to treat chronic wounds.

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